

Quantum and Classical Mechanics and Two Delivery Schemes for Force

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 3, 2023

In this note we argue there exist two force delivery schemes which are already well-known in classical mechanics namely: $F(x)dx$ and $F(t)dt$. The former is associated with work and kinetic energy, is deterministic (yields $x(t)$) and requires information about velocity (or rest mass). It deals with $F(x)$ where $F=Force$. The second is associated with an impulse which changes momentum. In this case, one does not need to know the rest mass or velocity. For example, a particle with momentum p (this allows for many m_0, v pairs with the same p) strikes a surface and is reflected back with $-p$. It is also associated with probability as such a scenario exists for light reflecting and refracting from a surface. One does not know a priori the probabilities for these two phenomena so the problem is probabilistic.

Classical mechanics primarily deals with the $F(x)$ force delivery scheme, e.g. solving a differential equation(s) which arise directly from $dp/dt = F(x)$ or using Lagrange's or Hamilton's formalism. Ultimately one obtains the deterministic result $x(t)$. Although the notion of an impulse is well-known in Newtonian mechanics, it does not seem to be used much in calculations because an explicit form of $F(t)$ is usually not known i.e. the force acts in a very tiny dx region in a very short period of time. As noted above, both schemes i.e. both deterministic and probabilistic situations appear in the macroscopic classical world, yet for some reason it is suggested that Newtonian mechanics is only deterministic.

Newton considered a photon to be a particle with momentum p . A single photon reaching a surface with a different index of refraction has a certain probability to reflect and another to refract. This is a probabilistic, not deterministic, scenario governed by an impulse delivery. The probabilistic problem of light reflecting and refracting in a macroscopic situation may be solved by using continuity of the periodic electric field and its derivative from Maxwell's solution for a photon from his electromagnetic equations. We have suggested in previous notes, however, that no knowledge of Maxwell's result is needed. A steady state reflection/refraction problem removes time (unlike the $x(t)$ deterministic picture), but seems to require some kind of balance on the right and left hand sides of the medium. Furthermore two equations are needed to solve for the two unknowns (i.e. reflection and refraction probabilities). Intensity/flux does not balance because the incident and reflected rays have positive flux. For $n_1 < n_2$, it would be good to have a balance function which allows partial cancellation of the incident and reflected fluxes. The solution $\exp(ipx)$ allows exactly this and this solution only requires knowledge of p , momentum, not of rest mass (i.e. velocity).

Thus there seem to be two force delivery mechanisms in the macroscopic classical world with very different solutions. The first is the $F(x)$ delivery yielding the deterministic $x(t)$ and requiring knowledge of m_0 (rest mass). The second is the impulse delivery which is probabilistic, makes use of $\exp(ipx)$, and does not require rest mass. If rest mass is known, however, $\exp(ipx)$ is linked with the average equation $x = p/m t$.

At first the two delivery schemes seem mutually exclusive, but in the impulse situation, we try to show that a series of impulses may create the semblance of an $F(x)$. Thus one has the $\exp(ipx)$ from the probabilistic force delivery scheme, but at the same time an $F(x)$ emerges and so an

$x(t)$ type solution should also follow. How can this be? $\exp(ipx)$ is probabilistic and one may create averages with probabilities. Such an average or root mean square average may exhibit deterministic behavior. Thus $\exp(ipx)$ may be used together with a potential $V(x)$ to create a solution $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ such that the prms(x) behaves like a Force(x) delivery result, yet at the same time one has the features of the impulse delivery as $\exp(ipx)$ s are used. Thus the $\exp(ipx)$ impulse approach may be used in strict impulse delivery problems and in $F(x)$ delivery problems. This is exactly what occurs in quantum mechanics.

Classical Mechanics

Classical mechanics, as formulated by Newton, introduces both:

$F(x)dx$ (associated with work and kinetic energy) ((1a)) and $F(t)dt$ associated with impulse ((1b))

These two modes of force delivery are well-known. The problem is that if $F(t)$ exists at a tiny dx for a tiny time dt so $F(t)dt$ is difficult to calculate explicitly. On the other hand, $F(x) = -dV(x)/dx$ for conservative forces and the integral of $F(x)dx$ is readily calculable. Thus Newton's second law, includes both delivery mechanisms:

$$dp/dt = F \rightarrow dp = F(t)dt \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{or} \quad dp/dx \quad p(x)/m = F(x) = -dV(x)/dx \quad ((2b))$$

((2b)) readily integrates to: $pp/2m + V(x) = E = \text{energy} \quad ((3))$

One may use the deterministic ((3)) or solve for $x(t)$ of the differential equation: $m \, d/dt \, dx/dt = F(x)$. An oscillator is an example with $F = -kx$ which is readily solvable. Thus one gets the impression that Newton's formalism is solely deterministic with $x(t)$ being the only solution. This, however, does not seem to be the case as discussed in the next section.

Reflection/Refraction

The reflection/refraction of light from a medium with a different index of refraction is a problem which exists in the macroscopic classical world and is Newtonian, we argue, because Newton argued that a photon is a particle. It has subsequently been found experimentally that it has a momentum and may impart an impulse. An impulse is a concept from Newtonian mechanics. A main point, however, is that a single photon has a probability to reflect and another to refract, thus this problem is probabilistic, not deterministic. Thus Newtonian mechanics is linked to both the deterministic $x(t)$ result and a probabilistic one. For $F(x)$ one only considers a deterministic solution, but for the reflection/refraction of the photon one may solve for the probabilities to reflect/refract, but at the same knows $x=c(i) \, t$ where $c(i)$ is the speed of light in each medium.

How does one solve the reflection/refraction probabilistic problem? First consider a photon moving in the positive x direction with momentum p . It reflects ($-p$) and refracts $-p_1$. A traditional way to solve this problem is to use Maxwell's periodic electric field $Ei(-\omega t + px)$ ($\hbar=1$) for the photon solution of his electromagnetic equations. We argue, however, that one does not require

Maxwell's equations to solve this problem. One may see right away that for a steady state situation there is no time in the problem and that one requires two equations to solve for the reflected/refracted intensities (probabilities) in terms of the incident. The equation of energy conservation (LHS=early time, RHS =later time) with the energy of the incident, reflected and refracted photon being the same is:

$$AAp = BBp + CCp1 \quad ((4))$$

(This makes use of an additional equation $E=pc$ which is a wave result.) Given the steady state nature of the problem with time removed, one may write:

$$AAp - BBp = CCp1 \quad AA \text{ is the incident flux written as } AA \text{ to show explicitly that it is positive.}$$

Considering a difference of squares and leaving p intact yields the two required equations:

$$A+B = C \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and} \quad Ap - Bp = Cp1 \quad ((5b))$$

These immediately have the form of two kinds of continuity equations. In fact, thinking in terms of continuity of a linearly invariant function $f(xp)$ and its first derivative suggests that $f(xp)$ is periodic. This is further enhanced by the equation $A+B=C$. If $n1 < n2$, then $C < A$, so $B < 0$. If B is negative, it has the appearance of damping the periodic function associated with A . A periodic solution means p and $-p$ have the same wavelength and so $Af(px)$ and $Bf(-px)$ may be out of phase by 180 degrees and partially cancel. In order to have $f(px)$ map to spatially invariant value i.e. a constant one may use:

$$\exp(ipx) \quad ((6))$$

Thus the solution $\exp(ipx)$, which is probabilistic not deterministic, appears as a solution to this impulse delivery problem which exists in the realm of Newtonian mechanics. One may note that one could have proposed ((5a)) and ((5b)) a priori with $E=pc$ not being required. At the same time one has the deterministic solution $x = ct$ for the incident photon in a medium with $n1=1$, $x=-ct$ for the reflected and $x=c2t$ for the refracted where $c2=c/n2$. $C2$ may be measured experimentally just as c is measured in a vacuum i.e. $n1=1$.

Thus the impulse delivery solution $\exp(ipx)$ with $x=c(i)t$ is really a double solution and involves probability through $\exp(ipx)$.

Impulse Delivery Linked to F(x) Delivery?

In the above section we suggested there exist two delivery mechanisms, an $F(x)$ delivery and an impulse delivery and both exist in the macroscopic world of classical (Newtonian) mechanics. We now ask: What if one had many impulse deliveries distributed in x ? Each is an impulse delivery, but on average they give the impression of an $F(x)$. $F(x)$ delivery is associated with a deterministic $x(t)$ result. How can the two be reconciled?

It may be noted that $\exp(ipx)$ is probabilistic and has a fixed wavelength \hbar/p . Thus considering a wavelength, time is removed from the picture. Rather there is probability. If impulses are delivered, there are, on average, overlapping wavelengths which are physical. We suggest they are linked to the impulse needed to create p in the first place.. Thus one may suggest the following ensemble:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((7))$$

At present $a(p)$ are unknown weights of each impulse delivery solution $\exp(ipx)$. ((7)) implies the physical interaction mechanism in the problem is the impulse hit. Thus any notion of $x(t)$ or $v(t)$ would have to be some kind of average one. The fact that ((7)) involves different p values means there must be impulses in the system which knock one p to another. $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability scheme which is periodic in x and has the property:

$$\exp(ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((8))$$

Thus $\exp(ip_2x)$ may be seen as a periodic impulse delivery scheme acting on the periodic probability $\exp(ip_1x)$. $\exp(ip_1x)$, however, is a function of x because of this periodicity suggesting an $F(x) = -dV/dx$. It is known from Newtonian mechanics that each constant p is associated with a kinetic energy $pp/2m$ (nonrelativistic). Given a $V(x)$ one may use ((7)) to calculate an average kinetic energy:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ pp/2m \exp(ipx) \} / W(x) \quad ((9))$$

Why does one calculate $KE_{ave}(x)$ instead of another quantity? $KE(x)$ appears in the form:

$$KE(x) + V(x) = E \quad \text{from the } F(x) \text{ delivery scheme.}$$

One may consider $V(x)$ as being equivalent to the set of impulse $\exp(ikx)$ with weights V_k so $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$. Then in the impulse scheme, one needs the average kinetic energy as given by ((9)). We note that $\exp(ipx)$ involves $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ which have positive and negative regions. We have argued that these are linked to an internal force/acceleration encoded in $\exp(ipx)$ which is physical.

Thus one retains the impulse picture i.e. uses $\exp(ipx)$, but an $F(x) = -dV/dx$ emerges and so one must calculate a deterministic result, but it may only be some kind of average. In fact, $prms(x)/m = vrms(x)$ is the deterministic result associated with the problem, but one is more interested in the set of $a(p)$'s which then yield $W(x)$ which shows the periodic type result associated with the impulse delivery approach. This not simply a computation as $W^*(x)W(x) =$ spatial density and may be experimentally measured (in principle) to show there are humps in the density, something not found in the usual Newtonian $F(x)$ delivery scheme calculation. (We note in passing that the hump pattern is also found in 2 slit interference etc which is also an impulse delivery scheme calculation.)

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that in classical macroscopic Newtonian physics there exist two well-known force delivery schemes, namely the $F(x)$ deterministic, requiring rest mass approach and the impulse, probabilistic, not requiring rest mass approach. Thus one approach knows the velocity and the other doesn't. There is, however, a velocity in a problem with a specific rest mass, so the probabilistic solution (which excludes time) may be associated with a specific deterministic solution. (It is just that this m is not explicitly needed for $\exp(ipx)$ i.e p applies to a range of problems for which $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ etc. In particular, $\exp(ipx)$ is a probabilistic solution, but in a specific problem for which rest mass is known, there is a corresponding deterministic average equation $x = p/m t$.

The deterministic $F(x)$ approach ultimately leads to $x(t)$. The impulse approach, on the other hand, leads to $\exp(ipx)$ which is periodic, but maps to a constant through $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$. Only p is known and this is linked to an impulse type of reaction. An example of an impulse delivery problem in the macroscopic world is the reflection/refraction of light (or two slit interference etc).

Newton considered light to be a particle and a single photon has a probability to reflect or refract. Nevertheless, one may consider a steady stream problem which requires two equations to solve for the two probabilities. All intensities are positive, yet from a spatial balance point of view for $n_1 < n_2$, it would be good to have the incident and reflected light partially cancel to match the refracted light. This cannot be done with positive constant intensities in x , but $\exp(ipx)$ maps to such an intensity and is periodic. Thus one may have 180 degree out of phase waves which partially cancel each other. In addition, $\exp(ipx)$ is linked with an $x=c(i)t$ deterministic equation.

We have further seen that a probabilistic solution $\exp(ipx)$ may give rise to a deterministic result for an average or root mean square average. In this case, a set of impulses which may be probabilistically delivered throughout space is equivalent to $F(x)$ which is linked to the deterministic $F(x)$ delivery scheme. Thus one may still use the $\exp(ipx)$ s associated with impulse delivery, but they must yield the deterministic result as some kind of average. The equation $KE(x) + V(x) = E$ describes the deterministic $F(x)$ delivery problem, so one may use the $\exp(ipx)$ s to calculate $KE(x)$ average i.e. $\{ \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \text{ } p^2 / 2m \exp(ipx) \} / W(x)$. $\text{prms}(x)/m$ is then deterministic, yet $W(x)$ shows the humps associated with the impulse delivery approach. Thus there is a possible interplay between the impulse delivery scheme and the $F(x)$ delivery one.